

INTERCULTURAL CONFLICT, FACTORS THAT LEAD TO CONFLICTS IN CROSS CULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: This article discusses conflicts in intercultural communication, the main factors that lead to such conflicts, and effective ways to resolve them.

Key words: intercultural communication, conflict, problem, intercultural relationship, ethnocentrism, conflictology.

"Intercultural communication" is a special form of communication between two or more representatives of different cultures, during which information and cultural values of the interacting cultures are exchanged. The process of intercultural communication is a characteristic of this activity. It is a form that is not limited to knowing foreign languages, but also requires knowledge of the material and spiritual culture, religion, values, moral attitudes, ideological ideas, etc. of another nation.

American linguist Edward Hall was the first to conclude that it is necessary to teach the culture of communication with other peoples. According to him, the main purpose of studying the ICC problem is to study the practical needs of representatives of different cultures for successful communication with each other. The modern world is developing in the direction of expanding relations and

interdependence between different countries, peoples and their cultures. This process covered various spheres of economic, socio-political, social and cultural life of all countries of the world. Today, it is impossible to find ethnic communities that do not influence the culture of other peoples and the wider social environment that exists in certain regions and in the world as a whole. This was reflected in the rapid growth of cultural exchanges and direct contacts between state institutions, social groups, social movements and individuals of different countries and cultures.

Becoming a participant of any intercultural relations, people communicate with representatives of other cultures, often significantly different from each other, which makes these relations difficult, and sometimes impossible. The main reason for their failure lies in differences in worldview, for example a different attitude towards the world and other people. The main obstacle to the successful solution of this problem is that people perceive other cultures through the prism of their own culture. Representatives of different nationalities with great difficulty understand the meaning of words, deeds, actions, they are not unique.

It is known that intercultural relations go back to ancient times. Alexander Makedonskiy, Genghis Khan, Julius Caesar, Christopher Columbus, the pioneers of intercultural communication, the interaction and interaction of cultures, problems of relations between culture and language, as well as the search for optimal forms of intercultural communication. has always attracted the attention of researchers. Long before intercultural communication became a separate field of research, many questions that later became central to it were discussed by Aristotle, G.V. Leibniz, I. Kant, I.G. Herder, W. von Humboldt, L. Spitzer and others.

For the first time, the problem of intercultural communication appeared during the Second World War, when representatives of different countries had to solve problems of global importance together. Americans, who until now had followed

a policy of isolation, were faced with the need for intercultural communication. It was then that linguists, anthropologists, and communication experts—Margaret Mead, Ruth Benedict, Jeffrey Gorer, Weston La Barre, and others—for the first time in the United States gathered at the national level to explain intercultural differences and their "strange" behavior. stuck allies (Russia and China) and enemies (Germany and Japan).

After the end of the Second World War, the sphere of influence of American politics, economy and culture began to expand actively. Government officials and businessmen who have worked abroad often cannot cope with the misunderstandings that arise when working with representatives of other cultures. This often led to conflicts, mutual hostility and resentment. Even perfect knowledge of the relevant languages could not prepare them for the difficult challenges of working abroad. Gradually, an understanding arose about the need to learn not only languages, but also the culture of other peoples, their traditions, customs and norms of behavior.

Intercultural communication has its own patterns that fundamentally affect the interaction of the subjects of such communication.

A normal person cannot live without any disagreement with others, no matter how conflicted. "As many people as many opinions" and the opinions of different people will inevitably conflict with each other.

In modern conflictology, the emergence of conflicts is explained by various reasons. In particular, there is a view that animosity and prejudice between people are eternal and stem from human nature, due to its instinctive "dislike of differences". Thus, representatives of social Darwinism argue that the law of life is the struggle for existence, which is observed in the animal world, and is manifested in human society in the form of various conflicts, that is, conflicts for humans are the same. necessary for eating or sleeping...

Specific research refutes this point of view, which proves that hostility towards

foreigners and prejudice against any nationality are not universal. They appear under the influence of social reasons. This conclusion fully applies to intercultural conflicts.

There are many definitions of the concept of "resistance". Conflict is often understood as any conflict or incompatibility of interests. Let's note the aspects of the conflict that, in our opinion, are directly related to the problem of intercultural communication. Based on this, the conflict is not seen as a clash or competition of cultures, but as a breakdown of communication.

The conflict is dynamic in nature and appears at the end of a series of events arising from the existing conditions: situation - emergence of a problem - conflict. The emergence of a conflict does not mean the cessation of relations between communicants; behind it, on the contrary, there is a possibility of breaking out of the existing model of communication, and the relationship can be developed both in a more positive direction and in a negative direction.

The process of transition of a conflict situation into a conflict does not have a complete explanation in the special literature. Thus, P. Kukonkov believes that the transition from a conflict situation to a real conflict is carried out by the subjects of the relationship themselves, that is, the conflict acts as a "conscious confrontation". Conclusion: the carriers of conflicts are social factors, only when you define the situation as conflict, you can talk about the presence of conflict communication.

K. Delhes names three main causes of communication conflicts - personal characteristics of communicants, social relations (interpersonal relations) and organizational relations.

The causes of personal conflicts include clear will and ambition, violation of individual needs, low adaptability, suppression of anger, intolerance, careerism, passion for power, or strong mistrust. People with these qualities often cause conflicts.

Among the social causes of conflicts are strong competition, lack of recognition of abilities, support or unwillingness to compromise, conflicting goals and means of achieving them.

Organizational causes of conflicts are work overload, unclear instructions, unclear authority or responsibility, conflict of goals, constant changes in rules and regulations for individual participants of communication, deep changes or re-establishment of strengthened positions and roles. includes the structure.

Conflicts are likely to occur between interdependent people (eg business partners, friends, colleagues, relatives, spouses). The closer the relationship, the more likely conflicts will arise; therefore, the frequency of contact with another person increases the likelihood of a conflict situation in the relationship with him. This is true for formal and informal relationships. Thus, the cause of communicative conflicts in intercultural communication can be not only cultural differences. Often power or status, social stratification, generational conflict, etc.

Modern conflictology claims that any conflict can be resolved or significantly weakened if you deliberately follow five behavioral styles:

- competition - "The stronger is right" - this is an active style, does not seek cooperation. This behavior is necessary in a situation where one of the parties is eager to achieve their goals and seeks to act in their own interests, regardless of how it affects others. This way of solving the conflict, creating a "win-lose" situation, using competition and games, leads to the submission of one side to the other, using force to achieve their goals;

- collaboration- "Let's solve it together" is an active, collaborative style. In such a situation, both sides of the conflict seek to achieve their goals. Such behavior is characterized by the desire to solve problems, identify disagreements, share information, and see conflict as an incentive for constructive solutions that come out of the conflict situation. Since the way out of a conflict is to find a solution that is beneficial to both parties, this strategy is often called a "win-win"

approach;

- avoiding conflict - "Leave me alone" is a passive and ineffective style. One of the parties may recognize that there is a conflict, but behave as if avoiding or shutting down the conflict. Such a participant in the conflict hopes that it will resolve itself. Therefore, the resolution of the conflict situation is constantly delayed, various measures are used to silence the conflict or covert measures are used to avoid a sharp confrontation;

- compatibility- "only after you" - passive, cooperative style. In some cases, one of the parties to the conflict may try to appease the other party and put their own interests ahead of their own. This desire to convince another implies compliance, obedience and submission;

- compromise - "let's meet each other halfway" - with this behavior, both sides of the conflict partially give up their demands and come to a mutual compromise. In this case, nobody wins and nobody loses. Such a way out of the conflict is preceded by negotiations, the search for options and ways of mutually beneficial agreement.

In addition to using a specific method of conflict resolution, the following techniques and rules should be used:

- do not argue about trifles;
- not to argue with anyone with whom it is useless to argue;
- perform without strictness and strictness;
- try not to win, but to find the truth;
- admit that you made a mistake;
- do not take revenge;
- use humor if necessary.

Like any other aspect of intercultural communication, the style of conflict resolution is determined by the characteristics of the cultures of the parties to the conflict.

3 Most Likely Causes of Intercultural Conflict. Intercultural relationships can be incredibly rewarding and productive when they work well. However, when they don't, things can spiral into conflict fairly quickly. For example, couples might start arguing that their way of childrearing is the right way, corporate teams may stop communicating with their colleagues from other cultures; viewing them as untrustworthy or obstructive, or, managers of multicultural teams may see an increase in staff exits due to their inability to adapt their communication style cross-culturally.

Working across cultures is rapidly becoming the norm for most people across the world. As a result, intercultural conflict is also becoming more common. We'll look at 3 of the most common causes of intercultural conflict and give you some real-life examples of intercultural conflict in the workplace.

Cause Number 1 - Ethnocentrism

The most common driver of intercultural conflict derives from something known as 'ethnocentrism'. Ethnocentrism essentially stems from an individual's belief that their culture and way of doing things is the right way. There are lots of different levels of ethnocentrism, but an extreme ethnocentric will view the world quite simply as their experience of it.

They are blind to any other reality. Alternatives to their own way of seeing the world and interacting in it are quite unimaginable. An individual with this extreme view will have no concept of being a product of culture themselves - everyone else has a culture but they don't. The way they do things is right and the way everyone else does this is wrong! It's quite clear how ethnocentrism can cause intercultural conflict. A manager, who thinks that their way is the right way, will cause upset with his / her reporting staff, fail to listen to their needs, undermine their approaches and, quite likely, demotivate them. In a personal relationship, someone who feels their culture is superior and tries to enforce it will either destroy the relationship or, create a situation in which their partner is forced to

ignore their own culture and adapt to another – something that will undoubtedly cause resentment and upset.

Cause Number 2 - Differences in Cultural Values

Every culture has its own different set of values, and beliefs as to what is right or wrong. These values drive our behaviours. Take for example someone who places a great deal of value on time. They may even see time as money and resent people who waste their time. If you put this person with someone who doesn't place value on time, then this can provide fertile ground for intercultural conflict. In a different scenario, intercultural conflict is very possible if someone who values continuity is required to work closely with someone who values change.

Change can be perceived as threatening the status quo and harmony by those who value these areas. They may, therefore, not embrace it as quickly and may even be seen by others to be obstructing it.

Cause Number 3 - Cultural Communication

Different cultures have their own communication rules and their own ways of exchanging messages. In fact, it's fair to say that the way people communicate can vary greatly. In Asia and the Middle East for example, people rely less on words than people in the West and instead make great use of body language, facial expressions, silence and what is not said as opposed to what is said. There are a huge number of ways in which poor cross-cultural communication competence can cause intercultural conflict.

In conclusion, we have seen that there are many factors that can cause intercultural conflict. Although ethnocentrism, cultural values and communication style are three key factors, they do not stand in isolation- there are many other factors. Whether intercultural relationships are personal or business, it's essential that individuals recognise their own cultural frameworks and take the time to assess the values driving their behaviour. To ensure productive and fruitful intercultural relationships, then it's important to understand that one's own way is

not necessarily the 'right' way. Just different. By taking the time to understand the cultures we interface with, we are able to identify where intercultural conflict is most likely to happen and make efforts to ensure this is managed positively.

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